

Adopting Collaborative Business Processes to Prevent the Loss of Information in Public Administration Organisations

Authors : A. Capodiecici, G. Del Fiore, L. Mainetti

Abstract : Recently, the use of web 2.0 tools has increased in companies and public administration organizations. This phenomenon, known as "Enterprise 2.0", has, de facto, modified common organizational and operative practices. This has led "knowledge workers" to change their working practices through the use of Web 2.0 communication tools. Unfortunately, these tools have not been integrated with existing enterprise information systems, a situation that could potentially lead to a loss of information. This is an important problem in an organizational context, because knowledge of information exchanged within the organization is needed to increase the efficiency and competitiveness of the organization. In this article we demonstrate that it is possible to capture this knowledge using collaboration processes, which are processes of abstraction created in accordance with design patterns and applied to new organizational operative practices.

Keywords : business practices, business process patterns, collaboration tools, enterprise 2.0, knowledge workers

Conference Title : ICCASET 2014 : International Conference on E-commerce, E-administration, E-society, E-education and E-technology

Conference Location : Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Conference Dates : May 15-16, 2014